

A Contribution to Non-Destructive Inspection of Fibrous Plastics Composites with an Emphasis on Application of AE Techniques

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ABSTRACT

Acoustic emission of selected Fiberglass Reinforced Plastics (FRP) with flaws was examined. One group of FRP was after exposed to outdoor or accelerated weathering and other was after falling weight impact test, respectively.

In case of weathered FRP, AE from these specimens was apparently differed from that of the blank one depending on the weathering condition. It suggests that more detailed test shall be carried out in order to apply AE technique to outdoor FRP structures.

In case of FRP with flaws due to falling weight impact, a characteristic AE pattern was observed which may be useful to predict initiation and growth of cracks in FRP with such history of damage.

INTRODUCTION

Non destructive evaluation has been one of important problems to be studied to keep reliability and safety of fiberglass reinforced plastics (FRP) as high as possible. Recently acoustic emission (AE) which is vibrational energy released by formation and growth of flaws in materials under load attract attention as a promising method to inspect flaws of FRP nondestructively.

M. Takehara and et al. (1) reported about Kaiser effect and relation between AE and knee point of FRP of roving cloth. I. Kimpara (2) experimentally showed correlation between AE and knee point of FRP of roving cloth. K.P. Buhman and et al. (3) reported that AE depends on ply angle in case of FRP tube by filament winding. S.R. Williams and et al. (4) measured AE and stress relaxation and compared these with compliance in strain control fatigue tests. S. Amijima and et al. (5) reported that AE of various kind of GFRP under a certain level of stress was out of Kaiser effect.

AE of FRP above mentioned was all about that of sound FRP. AE of FRP with flaws was investigated by H.J. Schwalbe (6) and R. Prakash (7). H.J. Schwalbe measured AE of GFRP tubes with several kinds of flaws by internal pressure and mentioned in the report that AE from the flaws shows distinct increase in the total count over a certain level of pressure but that all of the flaws did not decrease bursting pressure. R. Prakash also tested GFRP tube under internal pressure and reported that high energy events of AE are associated with fiber failure and low energy events are with interfiber and matrix failures, respectively.

In this report, AE of mat FRP deteriorated by weathering was measured in tensile tests and that of mat FRP with cracks by falling weight impact tests was also measured in low cycle tensile fatigue tests, which were thought to be better than others in order to know influence of cracks to AE.

SPECIMENS, INSTRUMENT AND TESTS

Specimens

Specimens for Tensile Tests. Fig. 1 shows the configuration of specimens and location of transducers for measuring AE in tensile tests of weathered FRP.

The specimens (chopped strand mat 450 g/mm² x 3 ply) were handlayered up and classified into next four groups.

Group I : blank.

Group II : weathered for six months with no stress (from July to December 1976 at Higashimurayama branch of Mechanical Engineering Laboratory).

Group III: weathered with stress of 1/4 of bending strength (same duration and same place as Group II).

Group IV : weathered acceleratedly in chamber for 500 hours with stress of 1/4 of tensile strength.

Fig.1 Configuration of specimen and location of transducers for AE in tensile tests of weathered FRP.

Mechanical properties of the four groups of FRP are in Tab.I.

Specimens for Low Cycle Tensile Fatigue Tests. The configuration and the places of transducers for low cycle tensile fatigue tests of FRP with cracks were same as those of the specimens for tensile tests of weathered FRP (see Fig.1).

Table I. Flexural and tensile properties of weathered FRP.

	No.1	No.2	No.3	No.4
Flexural strength MPa	221	216	208	238
Tensile strength MPa	105	120	144	124

Fig.2 Apparatus to make test specimens with cracks.

Fig.3 Photograph of a type of cracks in FRP.

Table II. Physical properties of FRP with crack.

Cracks were made by the instrument shown in Fig.2. FRP sheet from which specimens for low cycle tensile fatigue tests were cut were set between two steel plates with 125 mm ϕ holes. The steel plates were bolted in order to clamp FRP sheet and a 225g striker was dropped on the center of the FRP sheet to make cracks. The cracks were from 3mm to 19mm long of several kinds of types, e.i. line-type, y-type and type radiating in several directions. Specimens for the tests were cut from the FRP sheets so that the longitudinal direction of the specimens were perpendicular to the longest dimension of the cracks. Fig.3 shows a photograph of a type of cracks.

Material	HLU	SMC
Thickness (mm)	1.5	3.7
Resin	unsaturated polyester	unsaturated polyester
Glass	chopped strand mat	
Glass content (wt%)	22.6	28.9
Filler content (wt%)	0	38.9
Flextural strength (MPa)	99	188
Flexural elastic modulus (MPa)	7350	12700

Table II shows the construction and the mechanical properties of HLU (handlay up) and SMC (sheet moulding compound) for low cycle tensile fatigue tests.

Instrument and Tests

AE was measured by the instrument (made by Aichi Sangyo) with an area analyzer to know the location of center of AE. Fig.4 shows the block diagram of the instrument. AE signal detected by the two transducers transmitted to the area analyzer through pre- and main amplifiers. The area analyzer not only shows the location of the center of AE but also reject AE signals from outer zone such as those by friction at clamps of test machine. Then event rate (Er), total event (Tev) and total energy (Ten) of AE was measured. Total energy of AE was the accumulated number of demodulated pulse of enveloped curve of AE signals. 10V of the enveloped curve of AE signals was demodulated to 1 MHz. Pre-amplifiers (40 dB, 50 KHz to 2 MHz) with 0.01 V threshold rejected electric noise and main amplifiers (40 dB, 50 KHz to 2 MHz) were set to reject AE signals under 100 KHz and over 700 KHz.

In the tensile tests of weathered FRP, IS-20 made by Shimazu were used at 0.5 mm/min of cross head speed.

In the low cycle fatigue tests of FRP with cracks, IS-20 was also used at 5 mm/min of crosshead speed (about 3cps) and during the tests, both of maximum and minimum load (OMPa) was kept constant.

RESULT AND CONSIDERATION

Weathered FRP

Fig.5 shows examples of AE in tensile tests of the four groups of weathered FRP. Final total event and final total energy per final total event were shown in Fig.6 and 7, respectively.

Compared Group II with Group I in Fig.5,6 and 7, it can be found that Group II specimen yielded AE at lower stress than Group I specimen and larger total event to failure and smaller energy per event were observed with Group II specimen than Group I specimen. These phenomena seem to be resulted from:

- (1) In case of Group I, not only matrix but also glass fiber fairly extended.
- (2) On the contrary, in case of Group II, comparatively smaller stress caused AE because of the matrix of the FRP deteriorated by weathering. It resulted in AE of smaller energy and larger number of events than the case of Group I.

Compared Group IV with Group II, AE of Group IV appeared at higher stress than that of Group II as seen in Fig.5. AE of Group IV has smaller total events to failure and larger average energy per event than those of Group II. These also seem to be resulted from:

- (1) Specimen of Group IV are loaded during the weathering (Kaiser effect).
- (2) The matrix of FRP in Group IV emitted less AE than that of Group II due to Kaiser effect and much more AE were shared by breakage of glass fiber in this case than in case of Group II.

As seen in Fig.6 and 7, AE of Group III was between that of Group II and Group IV. So it seems to show that degree of deterioration of the surface of outdoor weathered FRP was smaller than that of acceleratedly weathered FRP in chamber.

Fig.8 shows relation between total energy per total event and tensile stress per tensile strength of each group of weathered FRP. As found in these figures sudden decrease of curves are observed at stress nearly to $\sigma/\sigma_B = 0.9$.

From above mentioned, comparison of Fig.5,6 and 7 seems to be useful to know degree of deterioration of FRP by weathering. AE data-plot as Fig.8 is also useful to predict failures of FRP.

Fig.4 Schematics of instrument to measure AE.

Fig.5 Example of AE of each group of weathered FRP.

Fig.6 Total event of AE to failure of weathered FRP.

Fig.7 Average energy per event of AE of weathered FRP.

Fig.8 Change of energy per event of AE of each group by stress.

FRP with Cracks

For the first time, the specimen with the longest crack was tested in the low cycle tensile fatigue tests in order to know typical AE pattern of FRP with cracks. But the specimen did not break at the crack and typical AE pattern of FRP with cracks were not observed.

Except one specimen, all specimens were broken at section apart from pre-made cracks by falling weight impact. S-N curves of them were shown in Fig.9.

Fig.9 S-N curve of FRP with cracks.

Fig.10 shows event rate (Er), total event (Tev) and total energy (Ten) of AE of HLU in low cycle tensile fatigue tests. In the last one or two cycles of load just before fracture, AE of more events and larger energy were observed. Before such last one or two cycles, AE of small energy which number of event increased proportional to the cycles of loads were observed. Therefore the authors understand it might be difficult to employ simple technique in predicting catastrophic failure due to fatigue.

Fig.10 AE of HLU with crack in low cycle tensile fatigue test.

Fig.11 shows AE of specimen which was only one example where the final breakage occurred after growth of the crack pre-made by the falling weight impact.

At 3,200 cycles, a crack made by impact test started to grow and at almost the same cycles, new cracks initiated and grew at the place apart 1/5 length of specimen from the location of the old crack. Tev and Ten increased suddenly by the growth of the new cracks. However, emission of AE soon ceased.

Fig.11 AE of HLU with crack in low cycle tensile fatigue test.

From 3,600 cycles, Tev suddenly increased again and at the same time, the old crack grew like a folding fan as shown in Fig.12(a) \rightarrow (b) \rightarrow (c). However, Ten did not increase in this region as found in Fig.11.

The specimen broke at the new crack which started and grew at 3,200 cycles and at that time, the shape of old crack was as shown in Fig.12(c).

Fig.12 Propagation of crack in low cycle tensile fatigue test.

Fig.13 shows an example of AE pattern in SMC under low cycle tensile fatigue tests. In this case, T_{ev} increased nearly proportional to the cycles. At the breakage of the specimen, many event of AE with large amount of energy were measured as in case of HLU.

CONCLUSIONS

From this investigation, the followings can be drawn:

- (1) AE of FRP in the tensile tests was influenced by the weathering conditions.
- (2) From the deteriorated matrix of FRP after weathering, many AE with smaller energy were observed.
- (3) Kaiser effect was also observed.
- (4) In case of low cycle tensile fatigue tests of FRP with crack, a typical pattern of AE was observed.
- (5) Many AE with larger energy were measured when new crack initiated and grew perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of the specimen.
- (6) But many AE with smaller energy was observed when the path of crack was pararell to the longitudinal direction of the specimen (see Fig.12).

Fig.13 AE of SMC without growth of crack in low cycle tensile fatigue test.

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